

MODELS OF OBJECT DETECTION SYSTEM IN VIDEO STREAMS ON A MOBILE DEVICE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the models of object detection systems in video streams on a mobile device and the principles of their operation. Important aspects of cameras for detecting objects on mobile devices are mentioned. In order to increase accuracy, it is recommended to work on errors and take measures to eliminate them.

When using mobile devices to digitize images of familiar objects, there is an additional option to use the digital camera's video stream in addition to individual photos or frames. The process of capturing an object using modern mobile devices involves the stage of "pointing" the camera lens at the object by the operator by displaying video stream footage on the device screen in real time for operator control. If the image processing is performed from a single image, the data contained in the original frames obtained are used only indirectly (by the operator). More visual information will be available when considering the

entire video stream as a digital image of an object.

The main difference between video streaming as a digital representation of a recognizable object is that a different sequence of observations is considered for the same object. Let us consider the reasons why the result of object recognition may be incorrect, based on the assumption that the system always acts deterministically, that the same input at any time and under any external conditions The results of the data set recognition are always consistent. Thus, any error is the result of the system not being able to distinguish this or that class object.

Recognition errors can be divided into three groups:

1. Errors caused by the imperfection of the recognition algorithm can be understood as errors that are “internal” in terms of the object recognition system and can manifest itself even with the ideal operation of other subsystems. This error class is an unconditional attribute of any recognition system, regardless of the input model.

2. Errors caused by defects in the supersystem. A single image detection system is, as a rule, one of the subsystems of a particular complex, and the images delivered to the input of the recognition system are formed as a result of the influence of other subsystems. As a result, errors can occur due to the imperfections of the previous subsystems. For example, suppose that an error occurred as a result of dividing the image of a text line into images of individual characters, resulting in the position of the right border of the image of the Latin letter "B". incorrect, resulting in the loss of the jumper between the two horizontal strokes in the image of the letter. The resulting image may not differ from the Latin letter "E" in terms of a single character recognition system.

3. Errors due to environmental noise. Such errors occur if, under the

environmental conditions in which the recognized object is located, its image becomes indistinguishable from the image of another class object. For example, suppose you are photographing an identity document that contains the “Name” field with the actual value of “PHOTO”. This area is written on a white background and the document is covered with a protective glossy surface. During the shooting, a flash from an external light source appeared in the document, completely covering the letter “P” and leaving the images of the remaining letters unchanged. Thus, the image of this field does not differ from the image of the "PHOTO" field in the same document.

Image Shaping Features for Digital Photo and Video Devices. We will consider the use of photo and video cameras to capture images of documents, while we will use the general term “camera photography”. Using lenses in a photosensitive matrix, light rays reflected from a shooting object during such a photography process form a document image. Compared to scanners, the optical design of the camera is more complex and in itself causes more distortion due to aberrations, glare and reflection within the optical system. The use of photosensors (matrices) and devices

to record images from analog electronics inevitably leads to the appearance of image distortions called digital noise. Digital noise sources are the process of digitizing an analog signal (signal quantization errors, thermal noise, and charging in the matrix) and further amplifying it. Additional sources of distortion are contamination of the matrix and defective sensor elements. Another source of distortion is image compression algorithms, which is especially noticeable for video streaming frames. Digital noise appears in the image as a mask placed on top of random color and brightness pixels. Noise is more noticeable in monochromatic areas of the image, especially in dark areas. Scanners guarantee high-quality lighting, unlike cameras, which often lack adequate lighting and the effects of digital noise are significantly enhanced. You can view the sizes of different devices to describe the documents. The default resolution for optical document capture systems is 300 dpi per inch. This resolution allows for quality recognition of printed text provided by all modern scanners and with the usual font sizes for printed documents. With this resolution, the A4 page image has a resolution of 3394x2400 pixels. The default resolution (5 megapixels) for a

mobile device camera in photo mode provides a frame size of 2592 × 1936 pixels. Thus, the maximum working resolution when shooting does not exceed 200 dpi (for A4 format - 2262x1600 pixels). The characteristic resolution of a mid-range webcam is determined by FullHD shooting mode with a frame size of 1920x1080 pixels, which provides even lower resolution, which can be calculated at about 120 dpi (for A4 format - 1358x960 pixels). Unlike scanners, when shooting with a camera, the document itself is in an arbitrary plane relative to the focal image plane. Deviation from the plane perpendicular to the optical axis leads to projective distortion of the document image. Assumptions about the flatness, parallelism, and perpendicularity of different parts of a document, such as boundary lines or text line images, are often used in OCR algorithms. Such properties apply to original documents and apply to images that are homotetic to the original document and obtained during scanning. Obviously, when shooting with a camera, angles and their proportions, as well as the proportions of objects, vary depending on the angle of shooting. This makes it impossible to apply classical algorithms directly, but

requires pre-projective normalization of the image.

Features of using video stream as a source of document images For a small-sized digital camcorder, the physical process of document image formation is similar to photo image formation. The image resolutions required for optical recognition can be considered high in terms of video recording technologies, leading to the need to transmit large amounts of data. The second is solved using hardware and software to compress the frame stream. Thus, when using a video camera image as a source in a document image optical recognition function, it is necessary to take into account the lower dimensions of the individual frame compared to using a scanner or photographic device. In this case, each individual frame of the image is subjected to packing / unpacking and may contain artifacts using missing compression algorithms. However, the use of video streaming allows the document to use a sequence of images for recognition, which can be located at different angles, in different lighting conditions, and in different focus conditions.

Models of object detection system in videoSpeed and Accuracy trade-off of video object detection (VOD) results in ImageNet VID. The blue points plot the state-of-the-art

(SOTA) VOD methods, and the red ones are our proposed method TransVOD Lite, achieving the best trade-off between the speed and accuracy with different backbones.

Video object detection(VOD) results on ImageNet VID

One good method is TransVOD, a new video object detection system based on the spatial-temporal Transformer architecture. TransVOD views video object detection as a problem of decoding / predicting the sequence to the end. In this method, it takes several frames as input and directly outputs the current frame detection through a Transformer-like architecture. In particular, we design a new transient transformer to simultaneously link the results of each object query and memory encoding. The temporary transformer we offer mainly consists of three components: a temporary deformable transformer encoder (TDTE) to encode multiple frame spatial details, a temporary query encoder (TQE) to combine object requests in a single video clip, and to receive temporary deformable

transformer decoder (TDTD). the final results of the current staffing determination. TDTE effectively aggregates spatial information through transient deformable attention and avoids background noise. TQE first adopts a strategy from coarse to subtle to select appropriate object queries in a single clip and to combine such selected queries through multiple layers of self-focus. TDTD is another decoder that takes TDTE and TQE outputs and outputs the final detection results. These modules are distributed for each frame and can be trained to the end. We can conduct a wide range of experiments on the ImageNet VID data set. Compared to the single-frame base, TransVOD achieved significant improvements (2% -4% mAP).

Based on the TransVOD system published in ACM MM 2021, we present two improved versions, including TransVOD ++ and TransVOD Lite. Because there is a huge surplus in both the number of object queries and the targets for TransVOD ++, we were able to extract the hard queries to select the most difficult queries during training inspired by solid pixel mining in image object identification and segmentation (HQM) strategy is presented. In addition, we introduced a new query and RoI

fusion (QRF) module via dynamic convolutions. In this way, object-level view data is included in each query and TDTE can be avoided because spatial synthesis can be replaced by QRF. Compared to the previous TransVOD, both improvements were found to lead to better results at a faster rate. In addition, when installing the Vision Transformer Trunk, we provide a simple custom fusion for TDTD to combine multi-dimensional features. After we adopted Swin-base as the base, TransVOD ++ ImageNet achieves 90% mAP in the VID data set and significantly suppresses previous work (5-6%) with a simpler pipeline. This method is the first method to achieve 90% mAP in an ImageNet VID data set.

Inherited from TranVOD, we introduced TransVOD Lite, which focuses on real-time VOD and modeling the VOD function as a sequence prediction problem adopted in machine translation. We take multiple frames as input and get multiple frame results at the same time.

The result of a single video clip can then be obtained in a temporary window mode. Thus, we can make full use of GPU memory to speed up the output time. TransVOD Lite can increase the base line of a single image by 2-3% mAP, but faster (4x-

6x). After adopting the Swin Transformer, our methods achieve the best speed and accuracy exchange. This method leads to a significant margin (3% -4% mAP, 5-15 FPS) compared to previous VOD methods in terms of speed and accuracy. The best model can achieve 83.7% mAP when operating at about 30 FPS. In short, after the TransVOD

system, we run TransVOD ++ and TransVOD Lite. Both models have set new state-of-the-art results in two different settings in the challenging ImageNet VID data set: accuracy for non-real-time models and best speed-accuracy sharing in real-time models.

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